

SOSfood Project: leveraging AI to create a Sustainable Food System

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Sustainability of the food system is global challenge with significant environmental, economic and social implications. In response to these pressing issues, SOSfood project advocates for the leveraging of data exploitation and AI technologies to enable informed decision-making across all stakeholders in the European food system, resulting in greater productivity, inclusivity, sustainability and resilience.

What is SOSfood?

SOSfood (Sustainable Optimisation for Secure Food System) is an innovative project focused on designing, developing and validating data-driven AI-based tools that can help all actors along the food supply chain to take evidence-based sustainable decisions, by identifying those causal factors that condition the sustainability of their activities and offering specific suggestions for its improvement.

Innovating Food Systems Through AI, Collaboration, and Impact

Tools

Providing dashboards for companies and mobile apps for consumers

AI & Data

Predictive tools for all food system actors

Impact Measurement

Assessing environmental, social, and economic impacts

Co-creation

Engaging the entire supply chain in collaborative efforts

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Funded by the European Union

Objectives and Approach

1. **Co-create a multi-actor and social innovation approach** aiming to:
 - Analyse the needs and expectations of all stakeholders to improve sustainability.
 - Promote transparency and data sharing.
 - Ensure the solutions proposed will adapt to each stakeholder.
2. **Design a framework to measure and weight impacts of the food system on sustainability dimensions:**
 - With a multidimensional strategy, exploiting the interoperability of data with advanced impact analysis and innovative AI-technologies
 - Using methods and metrics for the interaction among the defined scenarios and employing new ones derived from Artificial Intelligence for a dynamic multimodal impact analysis.
3. **Develop new predictive and clustering analysis methods based on machine learning (ML):**
 - Identifying and predicting the evolution of relevant factors with a significant impact on the sustainability of each actor
 - Developing new digital twins to predict and optimize the relevant sustainability indicators from a multi-stakeholder perspective.
4. **Develop and implement data-driven decision-making tools** for nutritional and sustainable food systems as a complement to the data spaces available to food system actors.
5. **Validate the innovation of the project through different agri-food systems** representing the disparities of the European territories, demonstrating applicability in other communities.
6. **Maximize the impact of the project** through dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

SOSfood Project Objectives

Tools developed

SOSFood will result in a **consolidated food data space** dedicated to the sustainability improvement of the food system and in **decision-making tools** adapted to each level of the food supply chain:

- A **predictive dashboard** displaying the data and prediction variables for industry users.
- A **mobile app** addressed to consumers, providing suggestions on fairer, healthier and more sustainable choices (including an eco-healthy fingerprint visualization plot, a green indicator of industries, and reformulated typical EU recipes promoting healthy, local and seasonal ingredients and general nutrition advice).

Industry Indicators

1

Provides forecasts and analysis for industry trends.

Predictive Dashboard

2

Measures environmental impact and resource usage within industry.

Sustainability Indicators

3

Ranks industries based on their environmental friendliness.

Greening Index

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Mobile app features

1

Visualizes user's eco-healthy footprint within the app.

Fingerprint Visualization

2

Provides reformulated local, healthy recipes for users.

Healthy Recipes

3

Offers general nutrition and sustainability advice to users.

Nutrition Advice

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To ensure the viability of the proposal and the representativeness of the developed algorithms, **SOSFood results will be validated in three case studies** at regional (Galicia), metropolis (Athens) and national (Lithuania) level.

How to Get Involved

People interested in supporting the SOSfood mission can:

- Adopt more sustainable lifestyle and food habits: reduce wasted food at home and in the community, reduce the consumption of red meat and dairy, purchase from local farms and suppliers, promote local seasonal vegetables and fruits.
- Contact us through our webform: <https://www.sosfood-project.eu/contacts/>
- Follow us on socials: [facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), Youtube
- Visit our website: <https://www.sosfood-project.eu/>

